

Preliminary Evaluation of RIDGEBACK 2 system for nuclear fuel analysis

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ABSTRACT

Each non-nuclear-weapon State Party is required to conclude with a safeguards agreement under which the International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA) act as the inspectorate. The verification process involves accounting of nuclear material, such as bundles or rods, to confirm their presence and quantify their content. This can be accomplished using non-destructive techniques (NDA), such as emission tomography, where emitted radiation is utilized to obtain internal information about an item without altering or damaging it. Verification of nuclear material is particularly critical for spent fuel, as it is an asset for recycling and a challenge for waste management. However, its handling is particularly difficult and expensive. Thus, advanced tomographic methods that are adaptable to spatial and geometric constraints, such as limited-angle tomography (LAT), offer promising potential as flexible and reliable assessment tools. This paper proposes the application of gamma-emission limited-angle tomography technique for the analysis of nuclear material, through a system named RIDGEBACK 2. The approach is demonstrated through simulations of a fuel rod and tomography system in Geant4, with data analysis performed in MATLAB. To evaluate the feasibility of the technique, the localization and quantification of filled and empty fuel pellets is performed, along with a comparative analysis of quantitative metrics between traditional and limited-angle tomography.

Keywords: Safeguards, Spent Fuel, Gamma-Emission Tomography, Limited-Angle, Geant4

1. INTRODUCTION

As part of the Treaty on the Non-Proliferation of Nuclear Weapons (NPT), each Member State must comply with a Comprehensive Safeguards Agreement (CSA), under which the International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA) act as the safeguards inspectorate to verify compliance. The verification process involves accountancy and control of nuclear material, or items, such as fuel assemblies, bundles or rods, or containers with uranium and plutonium compounds [1]. Its goal is to determine the presence, integrity, and quantity of declared items, which can be done by analyzing their gamma radiation emissions; as most of the materials emit this type of radiation. Implementation of Non-Destructive Analysis (NDA) techniques, such as emission-gamma tomography, are particularly useful as they provide internal information without damaging, or changing physically, the item.

Verification of nuclear material is particularly important following removal of fuel from a reactor, as spent fuel represents both a valuable resource, since it is considered an asset for resource recovery and a significant waste management challenge [2]. However, the handling and measurement of spent fuel is considerably more complex and costly than those for fresh fuel. The high activities of freshly discharged fuel can limit statistically representative sampling plans, and degrade performance of NDA systems [2].

To address these challenges, advanced tomography techniques have been focused on improving assay methods by employing high-resolution high-efficiency detectors, and optimize scanning methods, to reduce measurement time while maintaining reliability. This paper evaluates the feasibility of a gamma-emission Limited-Angle Tomography (LAT) system, named RIDGEBACK 2 in honour of OntarioTech University's mascot, for the analysis of nuclear fuel rods within a safeguards context. The

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study presents a comparative analysis between LAT and traditional Computed Tomography (CT) for the determination and quantification of filled and empty fuel pellets inside a mock-up nuclear fuel rod. Experimental data is obtained through Geant4 simulations, while the activity profiles are performed in MATLAB, enabling an assessment of the technique's potential as a reliable and adaptable tool for nuclear material verification.

2. METHODOLOGY

Safeguards activities require the identification of gross defects (i.e, removal of entire assemblies or rods), partial defects (i.e., missing or altered sections of fuel), and bias defects (i.e, small amounts of missing material). To address gross and partial defects verification needs, several non-destructive assay techniques exploit the gamma radiation emitted by spent fuel.

The IAEA currently employs Passive Gamma Emission Tomography (PGET) as one of its key inspection tools for irradiated fuel. The PGET system consist of two highly collimated CdZnTe detector banks that rotate 360 degrees around the item. This configuration enables high precision detection of partial defects inside of fuel assemblies, and ongoing research aims to improve angular resolution and enhance reconstruction quality [3]. Other gamma-based tomographic approaches have also been explored for nuclear fuel inspection, where studies have shown that collimator optimization, particularly through reduced aperture designs, can improve spatial resolution and image contrast [4, 5]. Additionally, work has demonstrated that iterative reconstruction algorithms, combined with prior information, can successfully reveal internal anomalies in complex fuel assemblies [6, 7]. Furthermore, alternative configurations using an increased number of detectors have shown potential to enhance statistical quality and reduce acquisition time [6, 8]. All these developments highlight the growing interest in improving tomographic techniques for nuclear material verification, particularly for challenging situations where high attenuation, complex geometries, and limited access are typical conditions of fuel assemblies.

2.1. Limited-Angle Tomography

Beyond the traditional full rotational scan (360°), more geometrically flexible techniques, such as limited-angle tomography (LAT), have been investigated for nuclear fuel imaging. Limited-angle methods restrict data acquisition to a smaller angular range, making them compatible with scenarios where space constraints, mechanical limitations, or in-pool inspection requirements prevent complete rotation around the object, or systems where shorter measurement times are needed.

LAT has been successfully applied in several contexts. For instance, neutron-based limited-angle tomography has demonstrated clear structural visualization and improved spatial resolution in fuel assemblies under constrained scanning geometries [9]. Although the majority of LAT literature originates from flat-object inspection and medical imaging, these studies consistently show that limited-angle approaches can provide in-depth information of the object and overcome transmission problems, and in specific cases, better image reconstructions than those obtained through traditional CT [10, 11, 12].

However, because LAT inherently produces incomplete sinograms, the resulting inverse problem is significantly more ill-posed compared to full-angle tomography. Consequently, LAT requires the use of advanced and computationally intensive reconstruction algorithms, often iterative, to achieve high quality images despite missing angular information.

Promising results from LAT in other fields have been seen. But its feasibility for gamma-emission imaging of nuclear fuel, particularly regarding pellet-level localization and quantification, remains insufficiently explored. This motivates the technique proposed in this paper.

3. PROCEDURE

To evaluate the feasibility of the RIDGEBACK 2 system for analysis of nuclear fuel, a simulation is carried out through the object-oriented program for the passage of particles through matter, Geant4 [13], followed by data preprocessing in MATLAB [14].

The RIDGEBACK 2 system consists of a steel-copper-lead collimator, based on [15] design, with a 1 mm aperture, and a CdZnTe detector modeled as a 0.125 cm² cubic crystal, following the design characteristics of the Kromek GR05 model. The scanning method employs a compound rotational-translational motion, as seen in Figure 1, to acquire data along a 500 mm long and 13 mm diameter cylindrical fuel rod.

Figure 1. Detector motion of RIDGEBACK 2 system over nuclear fuel rod.

The mock-up fuel rod is made of Zircalloy-4 cladding and contains 32 pellets separated by 0.4 mm gaps. Two pellets act as Zircalloy-4 end caps, while the remaining 30 represent the fuel pellets, as seen in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Left side: fuel rod with fuel pellets (in red). Right side: CdZnTe detector without collimator and crystal (in cyan).

Each pellet is modeled as a Cs-137 source, as the 662 keV gamma-ray emitted is the most intense emission peak from long-cooled fuel [3]; providing a more realistic surrogate for relevant safeguards gamma-emission measurements. The mock-up configuration is intentionally simplified to isolate and evaluate

the imaging performance of LAT under idealized, but safeguards motivated, conditions.

To assess performance, both traditional full-angle tomography and limited-angle tomography were simulated. For CT, 45 detectors were equally distributed around the full 360° rod's angle span, and each detector position was incremented 0.25° during acquisition to emulate a finely sampled rotational scan. For LAT, an angular span of 60.6° was selected, in which 8 detectors were placed every 8° and moved on the X and Y axis at specific positions, providing partial angular coverage. For both imaging modes, 10^5 gamma emissions were simulated at the center of each pellet, and four independent runs were performed to reduce stochastic variation.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this preliminary evaluation, the performance indicators determined quantification errors in distributed activity, pellet separation capability, and noise contrast. Thus, four activity configurations were simulated: a full rod, with 30 emitting pellets; a two-thirds full rod, with 20 pellets; a half-full rod, with 15 pellets; and a one-third full rod, with 10 pellets. For each case, the expected number of gamma emissions was compared with the number detected, and the mean axial position in Z-direction (length of the rod) of the counts was recorded, as seen in Table I.

Table I. Detected counts and mean z-position for CT and LA.

Cases	Traditional CT	Limited-Angle
Full		
$1.2 \times 10^7 \gamma$	Measured: $5.3 \times 10^5 \gamma$ $\bar{z} = -0.12 \text{ mm}$	Measured: $3.7 \times 10^5 \gamma$ $\bar{z} = -0.26 \text{ mm}$
Two-thirds		
$8.0 \times 10^6 \gamma$	Measured: $3.6 \times 10^5 \gamma$ $\bar{z} = 55.51 \text{ mm}$	Measured: $2.5 \times 10^5 \gamma$ $\bar{z} = 55.83 \text{ mm}$
Half		
$6.0 \times 10^6 \gamma$	Measured: $2.7 \times 10^5 \gamma$ $\bar{z} = 86.62 \text{ mm}$	Measured: $1.9 \times 10^5 \gamma$ $\bar{z} = 88.23 \text{ mm}$
One-third:		
$4.0 \times 10^6 \gamma$	Measured: $1.9 \times 10^5 \gamma$ $\bar{z} = 63.66 \text{ mm}$	Measured: $1.3 \times 10^5 \gamma$ $\bar{z} = 63.74 \text{ mm}$

Across all cases, the overall detection efficiency for CT remains above 4.4%, while LAT shows efficiencies between 3.0% and 3.2%. This reduction is consistent with limited angular sampling, where fewer projection views lead directly to fewer intersections between detector lines of response and the emitting volume; yet the efficiency difference is not drastic.

For the full-rod case, CT yields a mean Z-position of -0.12 mm, close to the theoretical value of 0 mm expected from perfect symmetry. These difference can be attributed to Poisson detection noise, or attenuation and Compton scattering in cladding, a common issue with gamma tomography. However, to assess whether these deviations are statistically significant, standard deviations (SD) and standard errors (SE) were calculated for selected cases, as shown in Table II.

Following Table II, CT and LA exhibit stable SE errors, where CT shows the best results in the range of $\pm 0.12 \text{ mm}$ and $\pm 0.14 \text{ mm}$, however the LA ranges only differ by ± 0.01 to $\pm 0.04 \text{ mm}$. This indicates that the limited angle approach is close to the expected distribution.

Table II. Standard deviation (SD) and standard error (SE) of the axial count distribution.

Cases	Traditional CT	Limited-Angle
Full	SD: 107.5 mm SE:± 0.14 mm	SD: 107.7 mm SE:± 0.17 mm
Half	SD: 63.58 mm SE:± 0.12 mm	SD: 62.67 mm SE:± 0.15 mm
One-third	SD: 56.16 mm SE:± 0.13 mm	SD: 55.05 mm SE:± 0.16 mm

Inspection of the axial activity distributions showed clear distinction of gaps between the pellets, and identification of empty zones. However, it also showed a systematic gap in all LAT cases, between 17.5 mm and 32.2 mm, independent of the filling configuration. This gap manifests as a persistent reduction in counts and significantly distorts the expected activity distribution (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Axial activity distribution: a) for traditional CT; b) for limited-angle.

Therefore, several diagnostics were performed to determine the cause of this persistent gap. The diagnostics evaluated the detector hit distribution, test of alternative angular positions, and increase of simulated number of particles. As shown in Figure 4, a heatmap of the counts per detector across the different detector rings positioned in the Z direction reveals a distinct band of low counts aligned with the axial region where the LAT gap appears.

This indicates a geometric under-sampling of the rod, where specific detectors within the limited angular span contribute with little or no information for that segment of the object. Consequently, a singular ring was evaluated in this range and showed that detectors 1, 2 and 3 registered less than 3 hits. Suggesting a strong dependence in the recovery of information. Thus, 11 different angular positions, within the same 60.6° span, were evaluated. In all cases, the gap persisted with counts between 40% to 46% of the average axial counts. Choosing positions with the highest hit fraction improved the local activity distribution by only 5%, being insufficient to remove the gap. Finally, to evaluate the gap behavior for greater particle numbers, simulations with $\times 1$, $\times 5$, $\times 10$ the original number of gamma emissions showed that the gap scaled proportionally with the number of photons. Confirming that the effect is not due to insufficient statistics, but rather a structural limitation of the acquisition geometry.

Figure 4. Heatmap of counts per detector over each ring positioned in the Z-direction.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The persistence of an axial gap across different activity distributions, different detector positions, and different particle statistics indicates that the effect originates from the inherent angular undersampling of the limited-angle configuration. In contrast, traditional scan benefits from full-scan angular coverage, which allows information missing from one projection to be recovered from another. LAT cannot compensate for these missing views, resulting in non-uniform sensitivity across the axial direction. This behaviour is consistent with the missing wedge artifact in LAT, where regions of the object do not provide enough information in the limited angle span and exhibit decreased reconstruction fidelity or, in this preliminary count-based evaluation, decreased detection probability. Therefore, future work requires a formal evaluation of a suitable angle span for a fuel rod, as done by [10]. Additionally, as this gap is a direct consequence of the tomography technique, it must be compensated in the image reconstruction process, by including apriori information of the system, or by adding stochastic or deterministic processes where a most likely outcome of the activity distribution can be forecast.

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REFERENCES

- [1] "Safeguards Techniques and Equipment." *International Atomic Energy Agency*, **volume 1**, pp. 1020–6205 (2003). URL <https://www.osti.gov/etdeweb/servlets/purl/20409707>.
- [2] "Guidebook on Spent Fuel Storage Options and Systems." Technical Report STI/DOC/010/240/3, International Atomic Energy Agency (2024).
- [3] R. Virta, T. A. Bubba, M. Moring, S. Siltanen, and et al. "Improved Passive Gamma Emission Tomography image quality in the central region of spent nuclear fuel." *Scientific Reports*, **volume 12**, p. 12473 (2022). URL <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41598-022-16642-0>.

- [4] L. Senis, V. Rathore, E. Andersson Sundén, Z. Elter, and et al. "Multi-parameter optimization of gamma emission tomography instruments for irradiated nuclear fuel examination." *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section A: Accelerators, Spectrometers, Detectors and Associated Equipment*, **volume 1057**, p. 168698 (2023). URL <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0168900223006897>.
- [5] V. Rathore, L. Senis, P. Jansson, E. A. Sunden, and et al. "Calculation of Spatial Response of a Collimated Segmented HPGe Detector for Gamma Emission Tomography by MCNP Simulations." *IEEE Transactions on Nuclear Science*, **volume 69**(4), pp. 714–721 (2022). URL <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/9714315/>.
- [6] R. Virta, R. Backholm, T. A. Bubba, T. Helin, and et al. "Fuel rod classification from Passive Gamma Emission Tomography (PGET) of spent nuclear fuel assemblies." *arXiv* (2020). URL <http://arxiv.org/abs/2009.11617>.
- [7] M. Fang, Y. Altmann, D. Della Latta, M. Salvatori, and et al. "Quantitative imaging and automated fuel pin identification for passive gamma emission tomography." *Scientific Reports*, **volume 11**(1), p. 2442 (2021). URL <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41598-021-82031-8>.
- [8] M. Mayorov, T. White, A. Lebrun, J. Brutscher, and et al. "Gamma Emission Tomography for the Inspection of Spent Nuclear Fuel." In *2017 IEEE Nuclear Science Symposium and Medical Imaging Conference (NSS/MIC)*. IEEE, Atlanta, GA (2017).
- [9] M. Abir, F. Islam, A. Craft, W. Williams, and et al. "Determination of optimal imaging parameters for the reconstruction of a nuclear fuel assembly using limited angle neutron tomography." *Journal of Instrumentation*, **volume 11**(01), pp. C01016–C01016 (2016). URL <https://iopscience.iop.org/article/10.1088/1748-0221/11/01/C01016>.
- [10] J. Zhou, C. Long, H. Zou, Y. Han, and et al. "Non-uniform sparse scanning angle selection method for limited angle industrial CT detection of laminated cells." *Displays*, **volume 89**, p. 103073 (2025). URL <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0141938225001106>.
- [11] E. E. Ghandourah, S. H. A. Hamidi, K. A. Mohd Salleh, M. N. Wahab, and et al. "Evaluation of Welding Imperfections with X-ray Computed Laminography for NDT Inspection of Carbon Steel Plates." *Journal of Nondestructive Evaluation*, **volume 42**, p. 77 (2023). URL <https://link.springer.com/10.1007/s10921-023-00989-z>.
- [12] W. Du, F. Iacoviello, M. Mirza, S. Zhou, and et al. "X-ray computed laminography: A brief review of mechanisms, reconstruction, applications and perspectives." *Materials Today*, **volume 86**, pp. 267–281 (2025). URL <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S1369702125000689>.
- [13] S. Agostinelli, J. Allison, K. Amako, J. Apostolakis, and et al. "Geant4—a simulation toolkit." *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section A: Accelerators, Spectrometers, Detectors and Associated Equipment*, **volume 506**, pp. 250–303 (2003). URL <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0168900203013688>.
- [14] The Mathworks, Inc., Natick, Massachusetts. *MATLAB version 24.1.0.2837808 (R2024a)* (2024).
- [15] L. Marwaha and F. Tondeur. "Response function of the CdZnTe SPEAR detector." *X-Ray Spectrometry*, **volume 40**, pp. 417–419 (2011). URL <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1002/xrs.1368>.